

Streaming Correction Method of Griffin for Gas-cooled Pebble-bed Reactor

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803632

ABSTRACT

Neutron streaming through voids between pebbles increases effective leakage in gas-cooled pebble-bed reactors (PBRs). Standard homogenization under-predicts this effect, biasing reaction rates and power. This work presents a streaming correction method integrated into Griffin's online cross-section workflow for PBR analysis. The P. Benoist formulation is adopted for the homogenized transport cross section, using collision-probability coefficients from a multi-pebble collision probability method model and pebble-wise flux computed with a P_0 transport correction. The approach applies to both diffusion and discrete-ordinates transport methods. Verification on a 1D R-geometry and a generalized PBR 2D-RZ problem against Serpent2 shows excellent agreement in k-eigenvalue and power distribution. In the gPBR case, considering the streaming correction yields control-rod worth within $\sim 1\%$ of reference values, whereas neglecting streaming underestimates the worth by $\sim 10\%$.

Keywords: Gas-cooled pebble-bed reactor, streaming effect, Griffin

1. INTRODUCTION

Griffin [1] is a MOOSE-based reactor physics application [2] supporting multiphysics simulations of advanced reactors, including pebble-bed reactors (PBRs), under the U.S. DOE NEAMS program. Its Self-Shielding API (SSAPI) [3] performs on-the-fly resonance treatment for pebble ensembles and homogenizes pebble/coolant media for core-level calculations.

Prior work [4] established a lattice methodology to compute flux-weighting across pebble types and burnups for homogenization. Conventional diffusion-coefficient homogenization assumes near-isotropic migration and therefore loses accuracy in PBRs where helium voids induce anisotropic streaming. Using homogenized total and first-order scattering to build the diffusion coefficient typically underestimates leakage.

The present study addresses this gap by formulating the homogenized transport cross section via the Benoist method [5], using the multi-pebble collision probability method (CPM) established in SSAPI [4]. The approach integrates seamlessly with the multigroup workflow and supports both diffusion and transport solvers.

2. METHOD

SSAPI partitions a PBR core into local zones characterized by volume fractions of pebble ensembles (fuel types, burnup levels, and dummy) and coolant, with corresponding number densities (user-specified or passed from a streamline depletion module [6]). For each zone, SSAPI computes self-shielded cross sections in internal pebble regions (fuel zone and graphite layer) and coolant. Fuel treatment adopts double heterogeneity with the two-stage slowing-down approach [3]. The multi-pebble CPM solver then supplies fluxes and CP data for homogenization. All reaction cross sections except transport are volume-flux weighted conventionally; transport uses the Benoist relation constructed from CPM-derived probabilities.

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2.1. Lattice Calculation

Interactions among multiple pebble ensembles and coolant are considered. Simple volume-averaging (e.g., VSOP [7]) is inadequate, especially when high-burnup and fresh pebbles are mixed. For example, the 1 eV ^{240}Pu resonance self-shielding would be misrepresented, yielding more than a +10% absorption error and a lowered eigenvalue [4].

A CPM-based formulation (energy-group indices suppressed) is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}\Sigma_{\text{tr}}\vec{\Phi} &= \mathbf{P}_p\mathbf{V}\vec{F} + \Gamma_p\vec{j}^- + \Gamma_{p\rightarrow c}\vec{j}^+, \\ \vec{j}^- &= \mathbf{E}_{c\rightarrow p}\mathbf{V}\vec{F} + \mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}\vec{j}^+, \\ \vec{j}^+ &= \mathbf{E}_p\mathbf{V}\vec{F} + \mathbf{T}_p\vec{j}^-, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with $\vec{\Phi}$ and $\vec{F} = \vec{Q} + \Sigma_{s,\text{tr}}\vec{\Phi}$ scalar fluxes and volumetric sources in internal regions of all pebble ensembles and coolant ($\text{NR} \times 1$); \mathbf{V} , Σ_{tr} , $\Sigma_{s,\text{tr}}$ are diagonal matrices of volumes, transport and transport-corrected self-scattering cross sections ($\text{NR} \times \text{NR}$); \vec{Q} includes fission and scattering sources from other energy groups. \vec{j}^\pm are outgoing/incoming partial currents at pebble surfaces ($\text{NP} \times 1$). \mathbf{P}_p ($\text{NR} \times \text{NR}$) is a block diagonal matrix, representing within-pebble and self-coolant collision probabilities. Γ_p ($\text{NR} \times \text{NP}$), \mathbf{E}_p ($\text{NP} \times \text{NR}$) and \mathbf{T}_p ($\text{NP} \times \text{NP}$) are first flight blackness, escape probabilities, and transmission probabilities of pebble ensembles and $\Gamma_{p\rightarrow c}$ ($\text{NR} \times \text{NP}$), $\mathbf{E}_{c\rightarrow p}$ ($\text{NP} \times \text{NR}$) and $\mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}$ ($\text{NP} \times \text{NP}$) are the coolant counterpart. Note that all CPs are evaluated using the transport cross sections.

CPs that involve the coolant region resort to the assumption that neutrons coming from pebbles or the coolant region are not differentiated but treated the same as isotropic and uniform sources in the coolant region, dropping source dependency in the CPs and leaving all of them expressed by $P_{c\rightarrow c} \simeq \frac{\bar{l}_c \Sigma_c}{\bar{l}_c \Sigma_c + 1}$, where the average chord length of the coolant region follows the Cauchy's formula $\bar{l}_c = \frac{4V_c}{S_p}$, S_p is the total surface area of pebbles. Details discussed in References [1, 4].

Eliminating currents from Equation (1) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}\Sigma_{\text{tr}}\vec{\Phi} &= \left[\mathbf{P}_p + \Gamma_p(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}\mathbf{T}_p)^{-1}(\mathbf{E}_{c\rightarrow p} + \mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}\mathbf{E}_p) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \Gamma_{p\rightarrow c}\{\mathbf{E}_p + \mathbf{T}_p(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}\mathbf{T}_p)^{-1}(\mathbf{E}_{c\rightarrow p} + \mathbf{T}_{p\rightarrow p}\mathbf{E}_p)\} \right] \mathbf{V}(\vec{Q} + \Sigma_{s,\text{tr}}\vec{\Phi}). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The first term represents first collisions without passing other pebbles, while the others account for multiple pebble passes. The eigenproblem is solved via power iteration with group sweeps. For each group, LU factorization solves the dense system. Specular boundary condition is a reasonable approximation for fine multigroup structures (e.g., WIMS-69 [8] or finer).

2.2. Homogenization

For reaction type x , conventional flux-volume homogenization is

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{x,g(\rightarrow g')} = \frac{\sum_i V_i \phi_{g,i} \Sigma_{x,g(\rightarrow g')i}}{\sum_i V_i \phi_{g,i}}. \quad (3)$$

The Benoist transport cross section is

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}^{\text{Benoist}} = \frac{\sum_i V_i \phi_{g,i}}{\sum_i V_i \phi_{g,i} \sum_j P_{g,i \rightarrow j} \frac{1}{\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g,j}}}, \quad (4)$$

where $P_{g,i \rightarrow j}$ denotes the bracketed operator in Equation (2). Prior work [9] employed the same Benoist expression in Equation (4) with alternative CP formulations, but did not state explicitly whether the CPs in Equation (4) must be transport-corrected, nor whether the total or the transport cross section should appear in that expression. In the methodology presented here, both the CPs and the reciprocal cross section in Equation (4) are required to be *transport-corrected* (not total) quantities, as demonstrated in Section 3.

For diffusion, $\bar{D}_g^{\text{Benoist}}$ is equal to $1/3\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}^{\text{Benoist}}$. For transport with anisotropic scattering, the first-order self-scattering is adjusted to enforce the outflow relation

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{tr}^{\text{Benoist}} = \bar{\Sigma}_t - \bar{\Sigma}_{s1}^{\text{Benoist}}. \quad (5)$$

Subtracting the conventional relation (keeping out-scattering intact since streaming modifies angular redistribution without altering energy) gives

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{s1,g \rightarrow g}^{\text{Benoist}} = \bar{\Sigma}_{s1,g \rightarrow g}^{\text{Conventional}} + \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}^{\text{Conventional}} - \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}^{\text{Benoist}}. \quad (6)$$

3. VERIFICATION

Verification covers (i) a one-dimensional (1D) cylindrical R-geometry core comparing SSAPI-generated multigroup data to Serpent2-generated sets, and (ii) the generalized PBR (gPBR) two-dimensional (2D)-RZ benchmark [10], focusing on control-rod worth and spatial power. Griffin diffusion (CFEM) and transport (DFEM-SN) solvers are exercised as appropriate.

3.1. One-dimensional Cylindrical-R Geometry Core

Geometry and reference setup. An infinite cylinder of pebble bed (radius 1.2 m) with a 0.72 m graphite reflector is modeled. TRISO specification: 8.5 wt.% UO₂ fuel; pebble fuel-zone radius 2.5 cm, packing fraction 8% (7.60 gU/pebble); 5 mm graphite shell; bed packing 60% pebbles and 40% helium. The Serpent2 [11] reference uses random pebble locations (-disperse) in a 7.6 m-long cylinder with 10⁵ histories per cycle, 100 inactive and 1000 active cycles.

Griffin configuration. The pebble bed is radially meshed into 15 regions (inner 8 cm radius cylinder plus 14 rings of 8 cm width). SSAPI lattice calculations employ WIMS-172 groups with precomputed local packing fractions; no condensation is applied for the core calculation. Diffusion calculations use CFEM on a 2D-RZ mesh with 4 cm cell size. Transport calculations use DFEM-SN with P_1 scattering, a 4×3 polar/azimuthal quadrature, and CMFD acceleration.

For additional comparison, a Serpent2-based 12-group set is prepared. Because the default Serpent2 diffusion coefficient D is conventional, the cumulative migration method (CMM) [12] is activated. Due to generator limitations (v2.1.24; reflective; single-region), a uniform infinite pebble-bed cube is solved for $\bar{\Sigma}_{tr}$, which then replaces the original; consequently, a single set is used across the bed and only diffusion is tested with these data.

Results. Table I compares Griffin eigenvalues to the Serpent2 reference ($k = 1.36467$). Without streaming correction, leakage is underestimated and k is biased high. With the Benoist-based correction, all k

values align with Serpent2. Figure 1 shows that the transport cross section Σ_{tr} from the Benoist formulation agrees with Serpent2 (CMM) across energy, omitting the transport correction in CPM degrades agreement.

Table I. Comparison of Griffin eigenvalues with Serpent2 eigenvalue (1.36467 ± 0.00007)

Transport Scheme	Cross Section Generation	w/o Str. Corr.		w/ Str. Corr.		Str. Corr. Effect $\Delta k/k$ (pcm)
		k-eff	$\Delta k/k$ (pcm)	k-eff	$\Delta k/k$ (pcm)	
CFEM-Diffusion	Serpent ^a	1.36953 ^b	+260	1.36592 ^c	+67	-193
	SSAPI ^d w/ Tr. Corr. ^e	1.36769	+162	1.36513	+25	-137
	SSAPI ^d w/o Tr. Corr. ^e	1.36771	+163	1.36402	-35	-198
DFEM-S _N P1	SSAPI ^d w/ Tr. Corr. ^e	1.36804	+181	1.36517	+27	-154

^a 12G calculation with one cross section zone in the entire pebble-bed core

^b With CMM option off

^c With CMM option on

^d 172G calculation with 8 cm-wide 15 cross section zones in the pebble-bed core (region-wise pebble packing fractions)

^e Transport correction applied to the multi-pebble CPM calculation and $P_{i \rightarrow j}$ in Equation (4)

Figure 2 shows normalized radial power distributions for seven cases: diffusion with Serpent2-generated (a) conventional Σ_{tr} and (b) CMM-based Σ_{tr} , diffusion with SSAPI-generated (c) conventional Σ_{tr} , (d) Benoist-corrected Σ_{tr} without transport correction and (e) Benoist-corrected Σ_{tr} with transport correction, S_N transport with (f) conventional Σ_{tr} , and (g) Benoist-corrected Σ_{tr} .

The following trends were observed:

1. (a): Power is skewed, higher at the center and lower at the periphery, meaning that the leakage is underestimated without the CMM option in the transport cross section generation.
2. (a) to (b): CMM increases the diffusion coefficient, causing more leakage and resolving power tilt.
3. (c) to (d) in comparison to (a) to (b): Benoist-based streaming correction gives almost the same

Figure 1. Comparison of Griffin and Serpent2 transport cross sections.

Figure 2. Comparison of Griffin and Serpent2 power distributions for a 1D core problem.

impact as CMM.

4. (c) to (e) in comparison to (c) to (d): Transport correction is essential in the Benoist formula, without which the streaming effect is over-corrected.
5. (f) to (g) in comparison to (c) to (d): The first order self-scattering correction of Equation (6) for the transport calculation gives the consistent streaming correction as the diffusion calculation.
6. (g) in comparison to (d): The diffusion calculation slightly overestimates leakage, while the transport calculation shows excellent agreement against the continuous energy Serpent2 Monte Carlo result.

3.2. Two-dimensional RZ Core (gPBR)

Model. The generalized pebble-bed reactor (gPBR) benchmark [10] specifies a cylindrical bed of radius 120 cm and height 893 cm containing 216,916 pebbles of radius 3 cm, with an average packing fraction of 60.73%. Each fuel pebble includes a fuel-zone radius of 2.5 cm with UCO at 15.5 wt.% and a TRISO packing fraction of 9.39%, surrounded by a graphite shell. Control rods are originally modeled as 18 discrete rods. For the RZ reduction, an equivalent annular absorber ring is constructed that preserves the total absorber volume and axial positioning. Above-bed B_4C density is preserved; the below-bed B_4C density is tuned to recover the 3D integral worth. The Serpent2 reference adopts a consistent 2D-RZ representation with 250/1000 inactive/active cycles and 10^6 histories per cycle. Core calculations use Griffin DFEM-SN transport with P_1 scattering. Region-wise packing fractions are obtained by analytic axial integration of disk areas, and 15 cross-section zones are used (thin top/bottom/peripheral layers plus an inner cylinder) to capture spectral variations and leakage near geometric transitions.

Results. Table II summarizes the rod-out/rod-in eigenvalues and the integral control-rod worth. Neglecting streaming underestimates the leakage into the control-rod region, which reduces local absorption and yields an integral worth that is low by approximately 10% relative to the Serpent2 reference. With the Benoist-based streaming correction in the SSAPI homogenization, the final worth agrees with Serpent2 within $\sim 1\%$, indicating that the CPM-informed transport cross section restores the correct net

current balance across the rod annulus.

Figure 3 presents cumulative rod-worth curves as a function of insertion (or equivalent absorber height in the RZ mapping). The conventional- Σ_{tr} case shows a systematically less slope in the mid-insertion range, consistent with the under-predicted streaming; the Benoist-corrected case closely follows the Serpent2 trend over the entire insertion range. Figure 4 shows azimuthally integrated power distributions and corresponding percentage errors relative to Serpent2. The conventional case exhibits a center-high/periphery-low bias, while the Benoist-corrected case removes this bias and improves the gradient near the bed/reflector interface. A mild axial tilt of approximately $\pm 1.5\%$ remains, attributed to the strong top reflector and the absorber-ring representation, but overall agreement with the reference is satisfactory for both integral and spatial metrics.

Table II. Comparison of Serpent2 and Griffin Results (Control Rod Out/In) and Rod Worth for gPBR 2D-RZ Core Problem

Code/Scheme	Control Rod Out		Control Rod In		Rod Worth	
	k -eff	$\Delta k/k$ (pcm)	k -eff	$\Delta k/k$ (pcm)	(pcm)	Error (%)
Serpent2	1.34935	2 (s.t.d)	1.23305	2 (s.t.d)	6,990	-
Griffin w/ Str. Corr.	1.35084	+82	1.23340	+23	7,048	+0.84
Griffin w/o Str. Corr.	1.35415	+263	1.24724	+923	6,330	-9.44

Figure 3. Comparison of cumulative control rod worth of Griffin to that of Serpent2 for gPBR 2D-RZ core problem.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A Benoist-based streaming correction has been integrated into Griffin’s SSAPI to homogenize the transport cross section and diffusion coefficient for gas-cooled PBR regions, using a transport-corrected, multi-pebble CPM lattice calculation. The method replaces the conventional transport cross section with a CPM-informed $\Sigma_{tr}^{Benoist}$ and, for discrete-ordinates transport, adjusts the first-order self-scattering so that energy is preserved while the angular redistribution is biased forward in a manner consistent with streaming. Verification on a 1D cylindrical core and on the gPBR 2D-RZ benchmark shows restored leakage and power-shape fidelity relative to continuous-energy Serpent2 for both diffusion and trans-

Figure 4. Comparison of Griffin power distributions with that of Serpent2 for gPBR 2D-RZ core problem.

port solutions. Notably, neglecting streaming underestimates the integral control-rod worth by about 10%, whereas the proposed correction reduces the error to within 1%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE), Office of Nuclear Energy (NE), under contract DEAC02-06CH11357 for UChicago Argonne, LLC, supported by the DOE-NE Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program. This research made use of Idaho National Laboratory's High Performance Computing systems located at the Collaborative Computing Center.

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